

PATIENT'S SATISFACTION ON GOVERNMENT HOSPITALS IN MADURAI

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Abstract. Using government hospitals offers several benefits and can be crucial for many individuals, especially in specific contexts. Affordability, Accessibility, Comprehensive Services, Public Health Initiatives, Training and Research, Emergency Care, Support for Low-Income Families, Regulatory Oversight, Crisis Response, these are the main reasons why government hospitals are more important. The purpose of this paper is to examine user acceptance, service quality, and patient's satisfactions using TAM & SERVQUAL approach as research model. Research data were obtained by using structured interview schedule. For the study, 160 respondents—patients from government hospitals—were chosen. The tools or software used to analyze data is SPSS.

Keyword: *Acceptance Model, Service Quality, Patient's Satisfaction*

1. Introduction

Government hospitals are a cornerstone of the healthcare system, offering essential medical services to diverse populations at affordable costs. They are crucial for ensuring that healthcare is accessible to everyone, particularly those in underserved or low-income communities. By providing a wide range of services, from emergency care to specialized treatments, government hospitals play a vital role in maintaining public health and addressing health disparities. They also contribute to medical education and research, often collaborating with academic institutions to train the next generation of healthcare professionals and advance medical knowledge. Additionally, government hospitals are instrumental in responding to public health emergencies and crises, demonstrating their importance in both routine and urgent care scenarios.

2. Objectives

To study patients Satisfaction through service quality, Patients Intention, Usefulness, and Ease of Use. Also examine the extreme impact on patient satisfaction and the level of impact of mediating variable Intention to Use.

3. Population and Sample

The population of this study was both inpatients and out patients of Madurai Government

hospital consisting of 160 people. Patients of Government Hospitals are declared as respondents for the research. Hence the sample of 40 respondents (both inpatients and outpatients) are selected from each Government Hospital with the help of **Judgment Sampling Technique**, through structured interview schedule. The details of sample number and the hypotheses of this study were shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Detailed Number of Sample

S. No	List of Taluk with Govt. Hospital	Samples
1.	Government Rajaji Hospital	40
2.	Government Hospital, Thoppur	40
3.	Government Hospital, Balarengapuram	40
4.	Government Medical College, Madurai	40

Table 2. Hypotheses

H1:	Perceived ease of use has a significant impact on perceived usefulness
H2:	Perceived usefulness has a significant impact on behavioral intention
H3:	Service quality has a significant impact on user satisfaction
H4:	Patient satisfaction has a significant impact on behavioral intention

4. Instrumentation and Data Analysis Procedures

4.1 Socio economic profile of the patients

The present study confines the Socio- economic profile of 160 respondents are gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income, occupation and Area of Residence. Parameters, frequency and their percentage of different variables are tabulated under Table 3.

Table 3. Socio economic profile of the Respondents (Percentage Analysis)

S.No	Variables	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender	Male	90	56.25
		Female	70	43.75
		Total	160	100
2.	Age	Below 20	18	11.25
		21-30	24	15.00
		31-40	49	30.65
		41-50	41	25.60
		Above 50	28	17.50

		Total	160	100
3.	Education	Illiterate	17	11.33
		Primary level	56	30.67
		High school	54	36.00
		Graduate	29	19.33
		Post graduate & Profession	04	2.67
		Total	160	100
4.	Monthly Income	Up to 10000	47	31.33
		10000-20000	84	56.00
		20000-30000	24	9.33
		30000-40000	03	2.00
		Above 40000	02	01.34
		Total	160	100
5.	Occupation	Agriculture	19	12.67
		Government Employee	10	06.67
		Private Employee	63	42.00
		Business	28	18.67
		Student	17	11.33
		House wife	23	8.66
		Total	160	100
6.	Area of Residence	Rural	98	65.33
		Urban	62	34.67
		Total	160	100

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table-3 reveals that Male respondents (56.25%) are higher than Female respondents. Majority of the respondents are in the Age group of 41- 50 (30.65%). Most of the respondents are studied upto High School (36%) as compared to other educational groups. Majority of the respondent's family monthly Income fall under Rs. 10,000 – Rs. 20,000 (56%). Majority of the respondents are working as a private employee (42%). Majority of the respondent's Area of Residence is rural area (65.33%).

This study used interview to obtain data needed. The questionnaire instrument was measured by using Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Interview was conducted to the patients of government hospitals

5. Results

5.1 Outer Model Analysis (Measurement Model)

Outer model analysis specifies relationship between latent variables and their indicators through testing of construct validity and reliability of research instruments.

a. Convergent validity

Convergent validity value is the value of loading factor in latent variable with its indicators

which must be above 0,7. The loading factor results of all indicators in model research were valid. Moreover, indicator was also declared as convergent validity if AVE value is greater than 0,5. The result of validity test based on AVE value was shown in Table 4.

Table 4.

Variable	AVE
Perceived Usefulness	0.922
Perceived Ease of Use	0.801
Intention	0.832
Patients Satisfaction	0.726
Service Quality	0.785

Source: Computed data

b. Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity value is determined by comparing loading value on intended variable that must be greater than loading value with other variables. Initial results obtained four indicators that did not meet discriminant validity requirements so it had to be retested (by removing indicators one by one to find best results). After four retries, final validity test eliminated four indicators, i.e. PE6, T1, T2, and AS4 indicators.

c. Reliability

Reliability test is conducted to find out whether the distributed questionnaire will be able to produce same results when it is conducted repeatedly. Reliability tests can be seen from Cronbach's alpha value (which must be greater than 0.6) and composite reliability value (which must be greater than 0.7). The reliability test results were shown in Table 4.

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Perceived usefulness	0.962	0.968
Perceived ease of use	0.946	0.951
Intention	0.902	0.911
Service quality	0.939	0.943

5.2 Inner Model Analysis (Structural Model)

Inner model analysis predicts causality relationship between latent variables.

a. Determination coefficient (R^2)

R^2 indicates the extent to which a construct can explain model to find out magnitude of the effect of particular independent latent variable on dependent latent variable. R^2 value must be greater than 0.7 to categorize variables as strong variable. R^2 value was shown in Table 5.

Table 5. R-Square

Variable	R ² Value
Perceived ease of use	0.832
Perceived usefulness	0.858
Intention	0.836
Patient Satisfaction	0.847

Source: Computed Data

b. Predictive relevance (Q²)

Q² value was acquired by formula: $Q^2 = 1 - (1-R^2)(1-R^2) \dots (1-R^2) = 0.999803$ From this result, the large diversity of research data that could be explained by structural was 99.98% and this model had predictive relevance.

5.3 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses testing was conducted on a research model consisting of 7 variables and 52 indicators. It was done by looking at t-statistics and path coefficient to 144 research samples. In this study, t-test was used with significance level of 5%. This result was shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Output Path Coefficient

	Original Sample	T- Statistics	Results
PEOU→PE	0.843	33.553	(H1) accepted
PE→BI	0.431	4.667	(H2) accepted
SQ→EUS	0.919	45.416	(H3) accepted
EUS→BI	-0.127	1.991	(H4) rejected

6. Model for this Research

6. Discussion

Research model purposed on section 3.1 Research Model has been examined on section 4 results. This section explained the analysis and detail of hypotheses testing results.

6.1 Effect of PEOU on PI

The results show that construct of perceived ease of use has significant positive effect on patient intention with the value of ($\beta = 0.64$). This perceived ease of use will make the patients to access hospitals easier so that the use of government hospitals will be increasingly perceived by them.

6.2 Effect of PU on PI

The results show that construct of perceived usefulness has lower effect on intention with the value of ($\beta = 0.19$) This usability will reduce the utilization of new technologies adopted for the treatments, which reduce their intention using facilities offered in the hospitals.

6.3 Effect of SQ on PEOU

The results show that construct of service quality has significant positive effect on perceived ease of use ($\beta = 0.49$). Good quality of service can meet or exceed patients expectations regarding their usage. so that their satisfaction of treatment technology will be increased.

Conclusion

Government hospitals, though service is an intangible that we cannot see or touch, have played a significant role in both major and little health concerns. Most people expressed satisfaction with the free medical care, cost and free medication, and level of service. Due to the fact that modern consumers demand the greatest possible deals, a reliable infrastructure, readily available technology, a wide range of payment options, and high-quality services. Half of the patients in government hospitals were not happy since there were not enough doctors, facilities, or technological developments.

Based on analysis result, there are correlations between user acceptance, service quality, and patients satisfaction. These correlations are the results from examining process of research model proposed. Moreover, based on 4 hypotheses proposed in model, there are one rejected hypotheses, which is hypotheses 4. To improve government hospitals implementation in the future, it is necessary to improve these three factors in accordance with indicators through model.

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